

Darby Project, Ottawa County (41.53431, -83.00600)

Since construction in 2021, the nutrient benefit of the Darby Project has been limited due to tradeoffs in management goals. Water level management at this Project prioritizes seasonal wildlife habitat needs, generally by adding water to wetland pools in the fall and draining them in the spring. From 2022-2024, the Project's two major pools were kept permanently inundated, but water levels fluctuated in both in response to seasonal patterns in management activities. Water chemistry data suggest periods of connection with LaCarpe Creek and the adjacent ditch when water level control structures (WLCSs) were left open in the late spring, allowing some nutrient-rich water to be received and filtered by the wetland pools. However, water chemistry data also indicate a lack of connectivity during key spring flows and other instances of high nutrient load.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is actively managed. This coastal Project has 352 acres of restored wetland featuring two major pools: a large western pool (Pool 1) and a smaller eastern pool (Pool 4). The Project receives water from a ditch that runs adjacent to Pools 1 and 4, as well as LaCarpe Creek that flows from south to north along the west side of the wetland. There are three WLCSs along LaCarpe Creek and the adjacent ditch, connecting them to Pools 1 and 4. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event where WLCSs are open, and water can flow into or out of Pools 1 and 4.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar coastal wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Promote increased nutrient filtration opportunity by “cycling” LaCarpe Creek water through the wetland pools once or a few times per year, especially by allowing water to enter the wetland in spring when nutrient sequestration is most impactful for preventing harmful algal blooms in nearby Lake Erie.

Project site restrictions (e.g., access to federal wildlife to reserve), barriers to access (e.g., dike conditions and hunting activity), and complex flow paths, as well as incomplete knowledge about water levels within the wetland units, limit the understanding that can be gained from this Project. As a result, sampling frequency by the Monitoring Program will decrease in 2025.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.